

Fabrication Of Magnetic Metal Separating Machine Using IoT

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Abstract

Treatment ways are aiming at the decrease of the organic carbon content so that the process output meets criteria for final disposal. This work focuses on the recovery of non-ferrous metals. Compared to other waste components, such as plastic, wood, or textiles, non-metals exhibit better reusability and higher market values. The production of metals from primary resources is limited in resources is limited in source and represents an extremely energy consuming process. These concelebrates must be separated to generate metal produce that exhibit sufficient purities for the utilization as secondary raw materials. The residues and the different metals contained in incineration ashes reduces the visual differentiability between minerals and metals to a point where handpicking is not particles.

Keywords: *Magnetic metal separation, IoT, Load cells.*

I. Introduction

1.1 Overview of the Internet of Things

The major idea of IoT is to endow with the network infrastructure through interoperable communication protocols and the software for a better data collection with a suitable connection, exchange of information through the nodes on several heterogeneous networks. Applications of IoT include, home automation systems of smart lighting, healthcare, pollution monitoring, and smart grid. Inappropriately, many connecting of devices to the Internet presents causes a more possible for cybercrime. Analyst Gartner estimates that in 2025 the IoT devices will be used by 64 billion, except tablets, PCs, and smartphones. Individuals and some companies using IoT devices cross the legal agreement. A smart refrigerator was hacked two years ago wherein it sends indecent spam by building the ice cubes. Baby alarms were used for eavesdropping on and still used to converse to the sleeping children. In the year 2016, the ever-largest Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack in opposition to Dyn, a provider of significant Domain Name System (DNS) services to companies like Netflix, Twitter, and CNN was done by hacking thousands of security cameras. And again, in the year 2017, Wikileaks divulge that Central Intelligence Agency.

Impurities such as V₂O₅ and NaCl, combined to produce deposits which are molten that damage the Researchers believe that the integration of IoT with public cloud increases IoT security gaps due to more impending attacks through stealing, and leaking of personal, accessing processing, and networked information. In totting up to that, further moneymaking IoT attacks were explored, like cryptocurrency mining or the ransomware attacks on medical tools, point-of-sale (POS) machinery, or vehicles. It is important to explore that what makes these devices are so vulnerable in IoT being a runaway train, never going back. Security is not made very crucial in the progress of these devices creating security on IoT devices with destitute, security absent may be costly, or else slow growth, or sometimes that survive the device performance approaches with term speed and efficiency. The devices that are directly borne to the internet have opened a backdoor to let the criminals in because of poor network segmentation. Researchers and marketers are engaged in a full range of solutions to protect IoT devices and networks. Instead, there's a long way to go before the standards are established.

1.2 Magnetic metal separating machine using IoT.

Magnetic Separation is one of the physical concentration processes that utilizes the differences in magnetic properties of various minerals present in the ore body. The magnetic fraction may be valuable or gangue depending upon its end use in a particular process and so also the non-magnetic fraction, e.g., separation of magnetite (magnetic) from quartz (non-magnetic), separation of tin bearing mineral cassiterite (non-magnetic) from magnetite (magnetic) impurity etc.

Selecting the proper magnetic separator requires an understanding of magnetic properties, the process application and environmental elements that exist in each specific installation. This guide provides a basic understanding of how to choose the proper magnetic separator for different process requirements. Head roll magnets are available in various magnetic strengths. A head roll magnet is mounted as a drive roller in a conveyor belt. Next, it will attract iron particles present in the product and deflect these to the bottom of the belt. There, the iron particles will be released from the magnetic field and collected in a funnel or a slide plate. Over belt magnets can be mounted both in line with and across the conveyor belt. All magnets have a short weakening pole at the end of the main pole, to promote the releasing of iron particles. A magnetic head roll is regularly used as a second deionization step in combination with overhead magnets, to realize a finer separation after the first separation of coarse steel particles.

II. Literature review

Sumardi Sadi et.al [1], studied the Design of separator based on PLC CP1E-E30SDR-A and Pneumatic metal and non-metal items is a prototype that can separate metal and non-metal goods working based on PLC programs with pneumatic actuators it works automatically. Making prototypes aims to simplify human work, especially in sorting metal and non-metal goods, to reduce the occurrence of errors in sort items, because if done manually it is likely that an error will occur because of the error factor.

Niranjana Sanjay Gaikwad et.al [2], have investigated the multiple steps in the recycling of non-ferrous metals is the separation of shredded material into separate groups. In our project, we propose the concept of "Metal & Non-metal Sorting Using Metal Detector". This system of sorting products is optimized to differentiate between metal & non-metals products, which is done with the help of a metal detector. A continuous conveyor belt carries the various products, and with the help of a control motor it separates metal from non-metal.

Shunping Xie et.al [3], have studied the Dry permanent magnetic separators have been widely used in the mineral and coal processing industries due to their simple operation and high separation efficiency. These tools not only discard some amount of bulk gangue from the raw ore, thereby reducing the volume of the grinding operation and cutting energy consumption, but also do not require water in the sorting process, thereby expanding their applicability to arid and cold areas.

Qin Xing Zong et.al [4], Studied the Magnetic separation is an indispensable part of magnetic separation, and the dry magnetic separator can be selected under the condition of water shortage in China to ensure that our country can also be selected under the conditions of lack of some resources. The magnetic separator plays a role in improving the grade of ore, purifying solid and liquid materials, and recycling waste. With the application and development of magnetic separation technology, magnetic separation equipment is constantly updating and replacing.

N. Chakravorty et.al [5], have investigated the Magnetic separation employs the difference in magnetic properties of minerals to effect separation between them. Magnetic separation may be for removing ore particles which are magnetic or conversely to remove magnetic impurities from a product which is non-magnetic. Examples are Magnetite from Quartz or Magnetite and Wolframite from Cassiterite.

Yohanes Dhimas Sigit Budoyo et.al [6], the study of Onion weight measurement recording in UD. Pangrukti Tani is still done using manual scales. Therefore, it is prone to errors in recording of the measurement. Based on the explanation above, a prototype of digital scale is designed to measure the

weight of onions using an ATmega2560 microcontroller which adopts Internet of Things (IoT) technology.

P.M. Sonsare et.al [7], As per the study people are getting smarter so are things. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a system of connecting mechanical and digital machines, animals or people with interrelated computing devices to provide an ability to collect process and transfer data over a network without requiring human interaction. While the thought comes up for smart cities there is a requirement for smart agriculture. As an example, this project presents a Smart weighing system which can be used for agriculture automation.

Hettiwatte MC et.al [8] have investigated the heavy mineral deposits of Sri Lanka are widely spread over the coastal area. The mining industry is looking forward to an effective method for heavy mineral separation with low cost equipments, which suits the local environment requirements to reduce the overheads. The major deposit at Pulmoddai, Trincomalee is a well-known Ulmenite deposit in Sri Lanka. The state company is currently engaged in processing imported separators, specifically magnetic separators for ore dressing.

Candra Ahmadi et.al [9], have investigated that the MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) in the village play an essential role in improving the welfare of business owners and consumers. MSMEs in the village meet the living needs of the villagers. Research is developing an IoT-based smart village transaction system using RFID and load cell modules. The research aims to simplify transactions in the village environment, which is unique to its agricultural and livestock businesses. The system was developed using a raspberry pi, the web server. RFID is used to record transactions made by villagers by scanning their resident cards.

III. Objectives

Based on the literature review, the following objectives have been framed.

1. Development of Fabrication of Magnetic Metal Separating Machine Using Iot
2. Implementation of IoT in Magnetic Metal Separating Machine Using Iot.
3. Generation of IoT, Arduino ESP8266EX, Microcontroller, Switch mode power supply, AC/DC voltage regulator.
4. Implementation of code in BLYNK IoT.

IV. Methodology

This chapter deals with Materials used for fabrication of Magnetic Metal Detector.

- 4.1 Procurement of materials.
- Main frame 20/20 MS tube.
- Conveyor 1.5 MM width.
- Geared motor 60 rpm.
- Roller 50 mm.
- Shafts 12 mm.
- Bearings.
- Permanent magnet neodymium.

4.1.1 Fabrication of the frame which is made of mild steel.

Fig 1. Fabrication of the frame which is made of mild steel.

4.1.2 Assembly of the magnetic metal separating machine.

Fig 2. Assembly with IoT components

4.2 Mechanism of Magnetic Metal Separating Machine.

Fig 3. Magnetic Metal Separating Machine.

This is the mechanism of a magnetic metal separating machine, consisting of a drive motor, conveyor belt, magnetic plate, and a roller motor.

4.3 IoT Components Used:

1. Arduino ESP8266
2. 10 kg load cell
3. Voltage regulator
4. ADC convertor

1. Arduino ESP8266:

Fig 4. Type 32-bit microcontroller.

1. Manufacturer Espressif Systems Type 32-bit microcontroller CPU Tensilica Diamond Standard 106Micro (aka. L106) @ 80 MHz (default) or 160 MHz Memory 32 KiB instruction, 80 KiB user data Input 16 GPIO pins Power 3.3 V DC Successor ESP32.
 2. Features Processor: L106 32-bit RISC microprocessor core based on the Tensilica Diamond Standard 106Micro running at 80 or 160 MHz [5] Memory: [6] 32 KiB instruction RAM 32 KiB instruction cache RAM 80 KiB user-data RAM 16 KiB ETS system-data RAM External QSPI flash: up to 16 MiB is supported (512 KiB to 4 MiB typically included) IEEE 802.11 b/g/n Wi-Fi Integrated TR switch, balun, LNA, power amplifier and matching network WEP or WPA/WPA2 authentication, or open networks 17 GPIO pins [7] Serial Peripheral Interface Bus (SPI) I²C (software implementation) [8] I²S interfaces with DMA (sharing pins with GPIO) UART on dedicated pins, plus a transmit-only UART can be enabled on GPIO2 10-bit ADC (successive approximation ADC).
2. 10 kg load cell

Fig 5. Load cell and amplifier board.

With this load cell and amplifier board, you can build your own scale in conjunction with a microcontroller or single board computer. The amplifier board contains an HX711 24-bit A/D converter to convert the analogue signal of the load cell into a weight with high accuracy. Due to its high popularity, there are many application examples online for this converter.

Table No. 1 Main Features

Main Features	
Model	HX711-10
Special feature	Integrated 24-bit A/D converter.
Measuring range	Up to 10 kg
Load cell accuracy	$\pm 0,02\%$ F.S
Items delivered	Load cell, amplifier board, pin header (4 pins)

Table No. 2 Specifications of Esp8266.

Specifications	
Supply voltage	2.6 ~ 5.25 V
Current consumption	< 1.5 mA
Interface	Serial; 2-wire
Dimensions PCB	34.2 x 20 x 3 mm
Dimensions load cell	75 x 15 x 14.2 mm
Cable length	25 cm
Weight	33.5 g

3. Voltage regulator

Fig 6. A simple voltage/current regulator.

Electronic voltage regulators are found in devices such as computer power supplies where they stabilize the DC voltages used by the processor and other elements. In automobile alternators and central power station generator plants, voltage regulators control the output of the plant. In an electric power distribution system, voltage regulators may be installed at a substation or along distribution lines so that all customers receive steady voltage independent of how much power is drawn from the line.

4. ADC convertor

Fig 7. Block Diagram.

An analog-to-digital converter (ADC, A/D, or A-to-D) is a system that converts an analog signal, such as a sound picked up by a microphone or light entering a digital camera, into a digital signal. An ADC may also provide an isolated measurement such as an electronic device that converts an analog input voltage or current to a digital number representing the magnitude of the voltage or

current. Typically, the digital output is a two's complement binary number that is proportional to the input, but there are other possibilities.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The separator was evaluated with beach mineral sand samples, by varying above mentioned parameters to find out the maximum operating values of those parameters. Sundried samples were used to reduce moisture (moisture 4%), which influences cohesion. Efficiency of the machine was checked with materials with known values.

Fig 8. Fabricated Magnetic Metal Separating Machine using IoT.

VI. Conclusions

Magnetic metal separating machines using IoT have been successfully fabricated.

Implementation of IoT in Magnetic Metal Separating Machine Using IoT, have successfully implemented.

Generation of IoT, Arduino ESP8266EX, Microcontroller, Switch mode power supply, AC/DC voltage regulator have been incorporated and implemented the code in BLYNK IoT.

VII. References

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